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Contribution to knowledge of the water beetles (Coleoptera: Adepaga, Hydrophiloidea) of Iceland, with unexpected observations on teratology

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Abstract: Based on our own, original, quite intensive fieldwork, which we carried out during a two-week entomological expedition to Iceland in 2018, we recorded 6 species of water beetle from 3 families; none were new for this country. This confirms the good state of knowledge of this country's fauna and also the typical paucity of water beetle species in circumpolar regions. Some families of water beetles, the members of which are common both in Europe and North America (Noteridae, Hydrochidae, Hydraenidae, Spercheidae, Elmidae, Dryopidae) are not represented at all in the Icelandic fauna. An unexpected observation, discussed at length in this paper, is the unusually high percentage of water beetles exhibiting teratological changes (3.48% of all the specimens caught), although these abnormalities related mainly to the number and shape of the antennomeres. We describe and illustrate these malformations, pointing out the need for the causes of their high incidence in Iceland to be further elucidated (> 3% versus < 3‰ among water beetles from other areas with which we are familiar). We also comment on aspects of morphology and, based on our field observations, on the habitat requirements of selected species.

Key words: Water beetles, shore beetles, Iceland, faunistics, Adepaga, Hydrophiloidea, teratology, high percentage.

INTRODUCTION

The water beetle fauna of Iceland is generally (and rightly) regarded as well known, probably because of the extreme paucity of species. To date, just 12 species have been recorded here, from the families Dytiscidae (5), Haliplidae (1), Gyrinidae (1), Helophoridae (1) and Hydrophilidae (4). One species from the family Hydraenidae (*Hydraena britteni* JOY, 1907) is known only from Late Holocene subfossil fragments and is not counted among the current fauna of Iceland. It probably became extinct during the cooling of the Little Ice Age following the medieval climatic optimum (BUCKLAND *et al.* 1991, ABELLÁN *et al.* 2011, VICKERS & BUCKLAND 2015).

Moreover, there are not a great many papers on Iceland's water beetles, and some information on the distribution of beetles during the past few hundred years (based on remains found during archaeological excavations) is contained in articles from disciplines other than entomology (e.g. BUCKLAND *et al.* 2004, SVEINBJARNARDÓTTIR *et al.* 2007, PÁLSDÓTTIR *et al.* 2008, FORBES 2013). The extreme paucity of species in Iceland, even though numbers of individuals can be very large, is typical of polar and circumpolar regions. This poverty appears to be due to the fact that, apart from its climate governed by its situation almost on the Arctic Circle, the whole island was covered by an ice sheet during the last glaciation. It was not until the ice receded that colonization of Iceland by plants and animals could begin, a process much complicated by the long distance from any continent (BUCKLAND *et al.* 1986). The nearest island to Iceland is Greenland (ca 290 km away), which is even poorer in water beetles, with records of just four species: *Colymbetes dolabratus* (PAYKULL, 1798), *Hydroporus morio* AUBÉ, 1838, *Gyrinus (Gyrinus) opacus* C.R. SAHLBERG, 1819 and *Helophorus (Rhopalohelophorus) brevipalpis* BEDEL, 1881. There is also one incidental record of *Cercyon obsoletus* (BÖCHER 2015). In no way, therefore, can Greenland act as a centre for the migration of species.

With the Internet version of the Catalogue of Palearctic Dytiscidae and Hydrophilidae (Coleoptera) (NILSSON & HÁJEK 2019; PRZEWOŻNY 2019), one has a useful tool for making rapid comparisons of one's own faunistic fieldwork results with the historical state of knowledge of the fauna of particular countries. Likewise, the printed versions of the relevant volumes of the Catalogue of Palaearctic Coleoptera have been recently updated and revised (LÖBL I., LÖBL D. 2015, 2016). All the more unexpected, therefore, is the omission from these catalogues of *Cercyon littoralis* (GYLLENHALL, 1808): we caught large numbers of this species, common in Iceland, in several localities, and regard these finds merely as confirmation of its occurrence in that country (RYNDEVICH 2003).

The aim of our study was to acquire possibly new data on the water beetle fauna of Iceland, and then to assess how well it is known by comparing our results with current knowledge of this subject using the updated Catalogue of Palaearctic Coleoptera, albeit with the above reservation. An unexpected and interesting result of our research was the high percentage of beetles we found with teratological changes.

Below we present original data for 6 water beetle species from Iceland, none of them new for this country.

The paper covers not only water beetles "*sensu stricte*" (JÄCH 1998), but also hygrophilic shore beetles and, for the sake of completeness, some coprophilic *Cercyon* species associated with decaying organic matter, caught near water.

TERMINOLOGY AND SYSTEMATICS

The terminologies and systematic arrangements of the water beetles are taken from the following sources: Dytiscidae – NILSSON & HÁJEK (2019); Haliplidae – van VONDEL (2015); Hydrophiloidea – PRZEWOŻNY (2019).

MATERIAL AND METHODS

We obtained the materials for this paper during a two-week field trip to Iceland in 2018. The beetles were caught using a lightweight, collapsible hand net in the larger water bodies and 1 mm mesh nylon kitchen sieves of various diameters in the smaller ones (puddles, flushes, pools). For obvious reasons we did not use a UV lamp and screen (polar day, no insects flying during the very brief night-time), and the bottle traps with organic attractants

that we deployed at a few sites were ineffective. We also used the flotation method along the edges of larger water bodies and peat bogs, and caught beetles on sight on the sandy sea shore under piles of decaying brown algae. The voucher specimens are in the authors' collections.

The localities are listed in chronological order, together with UTM codes and GPS coordinates expressed in the degree (°), minute (′), second (″) system. The place names are given in their original spelling, and information relating to microhabitats is also given. With respect to all the localities, all the beetles can be assumed to have been caught by both authors, i.e. leg. det. et coll. Czesław Greń et Krzysztof Lubecki.

1. ad Hella [WL28] 63°51′2″N 20°25′23″W, horse manure, 27.07.2018.
2. ad Hveragerdi [VM80] 64°2′30″N 21°13′4″W, pools and riffles in a stream in the Reykyadalur geothermal area, 27.07.2018.
3. ad Landeyjahófn [WL45] 63°37′6″N 20°2′8″W, pool by the River Markarfljót, grasses, mare's tail (*Hippuris vulgaris* L.), thread-leaved water-crowfoot (*Ranunculus trichophyllus* CHAIX ex VILL.), 27.07.2018.
4. ad Landeyjahófn [WL45] 63°36′59″N 20°2′16″W, horse manure on meadows in the valley of the River Markarfljót, 28.07.2018.
5. ad Þorsmörk [WL66] 63°40′36″N 19°36′5″W, water-filled hole on a grassy slope, 29.07.2018.
6. ad Þorsmörk [WL66] 63°40′51″N 19°37′44″W, small proglacial water body on the foreland of a branch of the Eyjafjalljökull glacier, 29.07.2018.
7. Kirkjubaejarklaustur, Lake Systravatn [XL47] 63°47′14″N 18°3′44″W, shore overgrown with sedges, 29.07.2018.
8. Fjallsárlón [DR39] 64°0′57″N 16°21′57″W, small proglacial lake on the foreland of a branch of the Vatnajökull glacier, 30.07.2018.
9. Kirkjubaejarklaustur, Lake Systravatn [XL47] 63°47′15″N 18°3′50″W, under an overhanging bank, stony bottom, 30.07.2018.
10. ad Djúpvogur [ES37] 64°39′26″N 14°18′47″W, under stones, 31.07.2018.
11. ad Stafafell [ES04] 64°27′17″N 14°56′8″W, small pools in a river valley, gravelly substrate, filamentous algae, numerous, also larvae 31.07.2018.
12. ad Stafafell [ES04] 64°27′26″N 14°55′48″W, a richly vegetated pool on meadows on a plateau, 31.07.2018.
13. ad Stafafell [ES04] 64°26′8″N 14°54′2″W, a pool by the road in the valley of the River Jökulsá í Lóni, gravelly substrate, club-rush and sedges, 31.07.2018.
14. ad Hallormstadir [ET12] 65°05′5″N 14°43′9″W, small, richly vegetated, peaty lake in woodland, marsh cinquefoil (*Comarum palustre* L.), bogbean (*Menyanthes trifoliata* L.), 01.08.2018.
15. ad Vopnafjörður [ET09] 65°45′43″N 14°48′47″W, beach, under brown algae, 01.08.2018.
16. ad Vopnafjörður [DT87] 65°35′9″N 15°20′48″W, 444 m a.s.l., small lake on a grassy plateau, 01.08.2018.
17. ad Vopnafjörður, Fuglabjarganes [EU10] 65°50′51″N 14°44′56″W, flushes on a waterlogged meadow, 01.08.2018.
18. ad Asbyrgi [DU31] 65°56′35″N 16°31′53″W, pool overgrown with sedges among volcanic rocks, by the tourist trail, 02.08.2018.

19. ad Kópasker [DU34] 66°14'26"N 16°25'40"W, beach, under brown algae, on sand, 02.08.2018.
20. ad Þórshöfn [DU93] 66°9'48"N 15°10'39"W, pool on a grassy plateau, sedges, cotton-grass, 02.08.2018.
21. ad Bakki, valley of the River Oxnadalse [XN17] 65°35'35"N 18°31'11"W, 04.08.2018.
22. Blönduós [WN38] 65°39'39"N 20°18'15"W, beach, under brown algae, 04.08.2018.
23. Blönduós, River Blanda [WN38] 5°39'38"N 20°17'56"W, 04.08.2018.
24. Öxnadalur valley [XN16] 65°31'18"N 18°35'33"W, 300 m a.s.l., pool on meadows by the road, very close to the shore, grasses, 04.08.2018.
25. Sæberg [VN93] 65°15'34"N 21°6'36"W, beach, under brown algae, on sand, 04.08.2018.
26. ad Flókalundur [UN97] 65°35'9"N 23°10'8"W, pool with cotton-grass by the tourist trail to Lake Helluvatn, 05.08.2018.
27. ad Reykhólar [VN45] 65°26'36"N 22°11'27"W, warm springs on meadows, pools, 05.08.2018.
28. ad Óspakseyri [VN86] 65°30'54"N 21°19'47"W, by the road, pool on a meadow, overgrown with sedges and cotton-grass, 05.08.2018.
29. valley of the River Hrófá [VN67] 65°35'44"N 21°45'44"W, tarn in a quarry bare of vegetation, submerged grasses, by the shore, 05.08.2018.
30. Dynjandi [UN99] 65°44'01"N 23°12'41"W, beach near the waterfall, under brown algae, on sand, 06.08.2018.
31. ad Brjanslaekur [UN96] 65°30'54"N 23°11'8"W, pool on a meadow, sedges, 07.08.2018.
32. ad Brjanslaekur [UN96] 65°29'17"N 23°16'18"W, beach, under brown algae, on sand, 07.08.2018.
33. ad Flókalundur [VN07] 65°34'33"N 23°9'50"W, beach, under brown algae, 07.08.2018.

Fig. 1. The map of the localities.

As the above list of localities shows, our fieldwork covered almost the whole area of Iceland that was possible to survey in two weeks. We focused on the area accessible to a reasonably robust 4x4 off-road vehicle, in other words, around much of the island's coastline and the road following it, without the inaccessible interior. We believe that we sampled every type of water body and watercourse present in Iceland, i.e. rivers, lakes, pools and other small water bodies, flushes, warm springs and proglacial lakes. Fig. 1 shows a map of the localities.

The positions of the localities are shown by blue, unnumbered squares. In cases where several localities are in close proximity to one another, the squares have been spaced out somewhat in order to retain clarity and to prevent misunderstandings regarding their locations. The white, numbered squares on the map show the route numbers in Iceland; we have deliberately left these in place as important information.

We include photographs of many of the localities in order to illustrate their variety (Fig. 2–25). Obviously, the list of localities contains only those where we caught water beetles; the surprisingly large number of sites where we failed to find any are not given.

RESULTS (FAUNISTICS)

We collected a total of 1089 specimens representing six species from three families.

Table 1. List of species

No.	Species	Localities
Dytiscidae		
1.	<i>Agabus (Gaurodytes) bipustulatus</i> (LINNAEUS, 1767)	2, 3, 5, 6, 7, 8, 9, 11, 12, 13, 14, 15, 16, 17, 18, 20, 21, 23, 24, 26, 27, 28, 29, 31
2.	<i>Colymbetes dolabratus</i> (PAYKULL, 1798)	14, 16, 20
3.	<i>Hydroporus nigrita</i> (FABRICIUS, 1767)	2, 3, 6, 8, 9, 10, 12, 13, 14, 16, 17, 18, 20, 21, 24, 26, 27, 28, 29, 31
Halipilidae		
4.	<i>Halipilus (Liaphlus) fulvus</i> (FABRICIUS, 1801)	3, 7, 9
Hydrophilidae		
5.	* <i>Cercyon (Cercyon) littoralis</i> GYLLENHALL, 1808	15, 19, 22, 25, 30, 32, 33
6.	<i>Cercyon (Cercyon) melanocephalus</i> (LINNAEUS, 1758)	1, 4

* – the fact that this species is not listed in the latest Catalogue of Palearctic Beetles (FIKÁČEK *et al.* 2015) is no reason for treating it as a species new to Iceland: there are earlier records of it from this country (RYNDEVICH 2003).

RESULTS (TERATOLOGIES)

Out of the total of 1089 water beetle specimens caught, 38 (3.48%) manifested teratological changes. This is an extremely high percentage, differing in the extreme from not only literature data (e.g. for Halipilidae van VONDEL (1986) gives a frequency of teratological changes of 0.02%), but also our own observations: in all our studies to date we have never recorded a frequency of such changes of more than 3%. All the more interesting, therefore, is the fact that these abnormalities in the water beetles from Iceland, though frequent, related mainly to the number and shape of the antennomeres (only in two cases was the sculpture of the elytra malformed – in *Cercyon littoralis*). Table 2 lists and briefly describes the malformations found, numbered in sequence and ordered according to species. The photographs appended at the end of this paper are numbered as in this table, so there should

be no problem with their identification. To save space, we do not repeat the descriptions of the malformations by the photographs – we wanted to include the largest possible number of illustrations. Even though the photographs of the localities are also numbered in sequence, they obviously cannot be confused with the photographs of the abnormalities. The specimens were photographed from such an angle as to best display the teratological changes. Usually, this means a view from above or of the whole specimen, or just of the pronotum and head, and only exceptionally from the front. It was not always possible to show the antennae straightened out, as attempts to achieve such an ideal view could have caused them to break off. We thus accepted their bent form; while this slightly distorted the picture as a result, it did not impair the discernibility of the malformations.

Table 2. List of teratological changes found in water beetles caught during a survey in Iceland in 2018

Species	Number of specimens	Description of teratological changes
1. <i>Agabus bipustulatus</i>	1	antennomere 7 of left antenna malformed, 10 and 11 truncate (Fig. 26)
2. <i>Agabus bipustulatus</i>	1	antennomeres 8 and 9 of right antenna adnate and malformed, 10 and 11 truncate (Fig. 27)
3. <i>Agabus bipustulatus</i>	7	left antenna with 9 antennomeres (Fig. 28)
4. <i>Agabus bipustulatus</i>	1	left antenna with 9 antennomeres, antennomere 9 truncate and malformed, vestigial (Fig. 29)
5. <i>Cercyon littoralis</i>	2	2 left distal palpomeres fused, intumescent (Fig. 30)
6. <i>Cercyon littoralis</i>	1	abnormal wrinkling of elytra (Fig. 31)
7. <i>Cercyon littoralis</i>	1	combination of 4 th and 5 th rows of punctures in the first half of the left elytron (Fig. 32)
8. <i>Colymbetes dolabratus</i>	1	right antenna with 10 antennomeres, 8 and 9 adnate and malformed (Fig. 33)
9. <i>Haliplus fulvus</i>	1	right antenna with 10 antennomeres, last antennomeres reduced, left antenna with 7 antennomeres, last antennomere enlarged and darkened (Fig. 34)
10. <i>Hydroporus nigrita</i>	1	right antenna with 10 antennomeres, 8, 9 and 10 of right antenna fused (Fig. 35)
11. <i>Hydroporus nigrita</i>	1	antennomeres 9, 10 and 11 of right antenna fused (Fig. 36)
12. <i>Hydroporus nigrita</i>	1	left antenna with 10 antennomeres, 10 truncate (Fig. 37)
13. <i>Hydroporus nigrita</i>	1	left antenna with 10 antennomeres, antennomeres 8 and 9 partially fused, 10 truncate (Fig. 38)
14. <i>Hydroporus nigrita</i>	1	left antenna with 7 antennomeres (Fig. 39)
15. <i>Hydroporus nigrita</i>	1	left antenna with 8 antennomeres (Fig. 40)
16. <i>Hydroporus nigrita</i>	1	right antenna with 8 antennomeres, on 8 traces of fusion of three antennomeres visible (Fig. 41)
17. <i>Hydroporus nigrita</i>	2	left antenna with 9 antennomeres (Fig. 42)
18. <i>Hydroporus nigrita</i>	1	right antenna with 10 antennomeres, 10 with vestigial antennomere 11 (Fig. 43)
19. <i>Hydroporus nigrita</i>	1	right antenna with 10 antennomeres, 8, 9 and 10 partially fused (Fig. 44)
20. <i>Hydroporus nigrita</i>	1	right antenna with 10 antennomeres, 9 and 10 partially fused (Fig. 45)

Species	Number of specimens	Description of teratological changes
21. <i>Hydroporus nigrita</i>	1	right antenna with 10 antennomeres, on 10 traces of fusion of two antennomeres visible (Fig. 46)
22. <i>Hydroporus nigrita</i>	1	right antenna with 6 antennomeres (Fig. 47)
23. <i>Hydroporus nigrita</i>	1	right antenna with 8 antennomeres (Fig. 48)
24. <i>Hydroporus nigrita</i>	1	right antenna with 8 antennomeres, 8 produced and malformed (probably fused from three) (Fig. 49)
25. <i>Hydroporus nigrita</i>	1	right antenna with 8 antennomeres (Fig. 50)
26. <i>Hydroporus nigrita</i>	2	right antenna with 9 antennomeres (Fig. 51)
27. <i>Hydroporus nigrita</i>	1	right antenna with 9 antennomeres, 9 malformed (Fig. 52)
28. <i>Hydroporus nigrita</i>	1	right and left antennae both with 8 antennomeres (Fig. 53)

DISCUSSION

According to the literature, 12 species of water beetle have so far been recorded in Iceland (including the coprophilic species from the genus *Cercyon*): *Agabus (Gaurodytes) bipustulatus* (LINNAEUS, 1767), *A. (Agabus) uliginosus* (LINNAEUS, 1761), *Colymbetes dolabratus* (PAYKULL, 1798), *Hydroporus nigrita* (FABRICIUS, 1767), *Nectoporus sanmarkii sanmarkii* (C.R. SAHLBERG, 1826) (NILSSON & HÁJEK 2019), *Haliplus (Liaphlus) fulvus* (FABRICIUS, 1801) (van VONDEL 2015), *Gyrinus (Gyrinus) opacus* C.R. SAHLBERG, 1819 (HÁJEK & FERY 2019), *Helophorus (Rhopalohelophorus) laticollis* THOMSON, 1854, *Cercyon (Cercyon) melanocephalus* (LINNAEUS, 1758), *C. (Cercyon) unipunctatus* (LINNAEUS, 1758) (PRZEWOŹNY 2019), *Cercyon (Cercyon) littoralis* GYLLENHALL, 1808 (RYNDEVICH 2003), *Cercyon (Paracercyon) analis* (PAYKULL, 1798) (GUDLEIFSSON & BJARNADÓTTIR 2002). The only record of *Nectoporus sanmarkii sanmarkii* from Iceland is based on four specimens caught at one locality near Skógar at the foot of the Sólheimajökull glacier (DUGMOR & BUCKLAND 1984). Likewise, the only Icelandic record of *Agabus uliginosus* is from just one site, to the west of Djúpavogur. It occurs there in a complex of small, shallow pools, at an altitude of ca 160 m a.s.l., on the peninsula separating the Berufjörður fjord from the Hamarsfjörður fjord (LARSSON & GÍGJA 1959, HARDARDÓTTIR *et al.* 2008, ÓLAFSSON 2011). The other three dytiscid species are common all over Iceland: *H. nigrita* and *A. bipustulatus* occur in all types of aquatic habitats, whereas *C. dolabratus* is found in small, usually thickly overgrown pools of somewhat greater depth.

During our two-week survey we found just 6 water beetle species, including the coprophilous *Cercyon melanocephalus*, out of the 12 so far known from Iceland (with the same reservation). We did not find any new species for Iceland. Since our searches in the field were quite intensive, and considering that we are sufficiently experienced in trapping water beetles in the field, we can justifiably conclude that the current state of knowledge of the Icelandic water beetle fauna is good.

From our field observations, it seems important to stress that water beetles in Iceland select microenvironments and habitats that are as warm and strongly insolated as possible. This applies even to those species that elsewhere are regarded as “cold-loving”, for example, the classical boreal-montane *Hydroporus nigrita*, which in warmer climates are found mainly in mountain areas, probably as a competition-avoiding strategy. These environments were therefore shallow, insolated and sun-warmed pools close by the shores of small water bodies and watercourses, where the water warms up during the day to much higher temperatures

than in deeper areas. Only there did we catch larger numbers of this species; elsewhere, we found just single or a few specimens. The obvious reason for this “thermophily” appears to be the lack of competition in these habitats, which is the effect of ecological (“island”) release. The same applies to *Colymbetes dolabratus*, which we found in slightly deeper, but always well insulated standing waters.

Agabus bipustulatus, well-known for its unusual variability, exhibited precisely this in Iceland, where a good proportion of specimens might once have been classified as *Agabus solieri*. At present, this specific name is synonymized with *A. bipustulatus* and is regarded solely as an ecotype characteristic of montane areas and colder water bodies. In Iceland, *A. bipustulatus* displayed its whole range of variability: specimens of the *solieri* type were found alongside typical ones in the same water bodies. Most of the specimens were very small ones, with body lengths of 9.0-10.0 mm, characteristic of the *solieri* type in different parts of Europe, e.g. Fauna Bulgarica: *bipustulatus* 10.0-11.6 mm, *solieri* 9-10.1 mm (GUÉORGUIEV 1987), Fauna d'Italia: *bipustulatus* 9.5-11.5 mm, *solieri* 9-10.5 mm (FRANCISCOLO 1979); The Freshwater Fauna of Poland [Fauna Słodkowodna Polski]: *bipustulatus* 10.0-11.5 mm, *solieri* 9-10 mm (GALEWSKI & TRANDA 1978). The smallest specimens we caught were 9.0 mm long, and the largest ones were 10.5 mm in length. Also quite characteristic is the fact that specimens from areas with a cooler climate are not only sometimes smaller (shorter), they are also on average narrower than their conspecifics from warm regions. With regard to *Agabus bipustulatus* this variability is well demonstrated in photograph (Fig. 54), where a wide-bodied specimen from Majorca, a typical specimen and a small one of the *solieri* type from Iceland are compared side by side. Solely as a fascinating observation, though bordering on unprovable speculation, we have noticed a similar relationship at the generic level, which is excellently illustrated by a comparison specimens of circumpolar *Colymbetes dolabratus* with the Palearctic *Colymbetes striatus* (Fig. 55).

As already mentioned in the Results section, the teratological changes found in Icelandic beetles, though very frequent, basically affected only the number and shape of the antennomeres. We do not know the cause of these malformations: we can only surmise that low temperatures during the preimaginal period (the larval and pupal stages) may be responsible. Of these developmental stages it is the pupa in particular, being the terrestrial stage in these beetles, that appears to be exposed to low temperatures, especially at night. The temperature of the aquatic environment in which the larvae live is, of course, more stable here. The analogy to frostbite, found in vertebrates, is probable insofar as it affects the peripheral parts of the body which are more exposed to cooling, and consequently, to developmental disorders and/or necrosis. An interesting and as yet unexplained question is the observed significant difference in the frequency of the respective teratological changes in the right and left antennae: in *Agabus bipustulatus* the ratio is 11:1 in favour of the left side, while in *Hydroporus nigrita* it is 15:9 in favour of the right side. The cause of these different frequencies on the left and right sides may lie in the position of the pupa in its cocoon, which can be different in different species. If the pupa is lying on its side, its upper surface is more exposed to cold, while the lower surface is sheltered – in Iceland at night, the cold comes from the air above, whereas the ground is a reservoir of warmth.

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Fig. 2. Locality no. 18 from the list locality.

Fig. 3. Locality no. 28 from the list locality.

Fig. 4. Locality no. 6 from the list locality.

Fig. 5. Locality no. 31 from the list locality.

Fig. 6. Locality no. 26 from the list locality.

Fig. 7. Locality no. 27 from the list locality.

Fig. 8. Locality no. 29 from the list locality.

Fig. 9. Locality no. 25 from the list locality.

Fig. 10. Locality no. 21 from the list locality.

Fig. 11. Locality no. 19 from the list locality.

Fig. 12. Locality no. 20 from the list locality.

Fig. 13. Locality no. 15 from the list locality.

Fig. 14. Locality no. 17 from the list locality.

Fig. 15. Locality no. 16 from the list locality.

Fig. 16. Locality no. 14 from the list locality.

Fig. 17. Locality no. 13 from the list locality.

Fig. 18. Locality no. 12 from the list locality.

Fig. 19. Locality no. 11 from the list locality.

Fig. 20. Locality no. 7 from the list locality.

Fig. 21. Locality no. 6 from the list locality.

Fig. 22. Locality no. 5 from the list locality.

Fig. 23. Locality no. 4 from the list locality.

Fig. 24. Locality no. 3 from the list locality.

Fig. 25. Locality no. 2 from the list locality.

Fig. 26. Teratology of *Agabus bipustulatus* 1.

Fig. 27. Teratology of *Agabus bipustulatus* 2.

Fig. 28. Teratology of *Agabus bipustulatus* 3.

Fig. 29. Teratology of *Agabus bipustulatus* 4.

Fig. 30. Teratology of *Cercyon littoralis* 5.

Fig. 31. Teratology of *Cercyon littoralis* 6.

Fig. 32. Teratology of *Cercyon littoralis* 7.

Fig. 33. Teratology of *Colymbetes dolabratus* 8.

Fig. 34. Teratology of *Haliplus fulvus* 9.

Fig. 35. Teratology of *Hydroporus nigrita* 10.

Fig. 36. Teratology of *Hydroporus nigrita* 11.

Fig. 37. Teratology of *Hydroporus nigrita* 12.

Fig. 38. Teratology of *Hydroporus nigrita* 13.

Fig. 39. Teratology of *Hydroporus nigrita* 14.

Fig. 40. Teratology of *Hydroporus nigrita* 15.

Fig. 41. Teratology of *Hydroporus nigrita* 16.

Fig. 42. Teratology of *Hydroporus nigrita* 17.

Fig. 43. Teratology of *Hydroporus nigrita* 18.

Fig. 44. Teratology of *Hydroporus nigrita* 19.

Fig. 45. Teratology of *Hydroporus nigrita* 20.

Fig. 46. Teratology of *Hydroporus nigrita* 21.

Fig. 47. Teratology of *Hydroporus nigrita* 22.

Fig. 48. Teratology of *Hydroporus nigrita* 23.

Fig. 49. Teratology of *Hydroporus nigrita* 24.

Fig. 50. Teratology of *Hydroporus nigrita* 25.

Fig. 51. Teratology of *Hydroporus nigrita* 26.

Fig. 52. Teratology of *Hydroporus nigrita* 27.

Fig. 53. Teratology of *Hydroporus nigrita* 28.

Fig. 54. Comparison specimens of *Agabus bispustulatus*.

Fig. 55. Comparison specimens of circumpolar *Colymbetes dolabratus* with the Palearctic *Colymbetes striatus*.

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